

INTERACTIVE TEACHING STYLES

Abduganiyev Abdukhalil ¹

Mamayunusova Manzura ²

Ergasheva Ziyoda ³

¹ Student of Namangan engineering-construction institute.

²⁻³ Teacher of Namangan engineering-construction institute

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Abstract: At present, modern teaching methods are widely used in education. The use of modern teaching methods leads to high efficiency in the teaching process. It is advisable to choose these methods based on the didactic task of each lesson. While maintaining the traditional form of teaching, enriching it with a variety of methods that activate the activities of learners leads to an increase in the level of mastery of learners.

Keywords: interactive methods, cognitive method, experimental method, role-playing games, modeling, facilitation method, educational effect, motivation, feedback.

Today, in a number of developed countries, the methods that form the basis of extensive experience in the use of modern pedagogical technologies that guarantee the effectiveness of the educational process are called interactive methods [1-2]. Interactive teaching methods are currently the most common and widely used in all types of educational institutions. However, there are many types of interactive teaching methods, and they are now suitable for the purpose of accomplishing almost all the tasks of the educational process. In practice, they can be used for specific purposes [3-5].

This has led to the problem of choosing the right interactive teaching methods to achieve certain goals [6].

Interactive methods are methods that activate learners and encourage independent thinking, with learners at the center of the learning process [7].

When using these methods, the educator encourages the learner to actively participate [8]. The learner is involved throughout the process [9]. The benefits of a learner-centered approach include:

higher learning outcomes;

high level of student motivation;

taking into account previously acquired knowledge;

adapting the learning process to the goals and needs of the learner;

support student initiative and responsibility;

practical learning;

Facilitate bilateral discussions.

Interactive teaching methods are often used simultaneously with various forms of learning technologies [10]. The use of these methods will increase the activity of the participants and improve the effectiveness of education.

Interactive methods of teaching.

1. Cognitive, primarily aimed at shaping the thinking of students (or learners), in one form or another associated with the organization of group discussion method.
2. Experimental, to the personal experience of the student (or students) focused
3. Role-playing games, Modeling, real-life modeling and a way to test them by playing certain roles team thinking, discussion-related, but discussion role-play analysis carried out on the basis of

Facilitation, (facilitate English facilitation) organization of group work, often making clear decisions about clear, realistic, practical assignments discuss and develop a realistic plan of action.

References:

1. Нормурадов, И. У., Сабирова, Р. Г. К., & Гойипов, А. Р. У. (2021). ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ ТЕПЛОВЫХ СВОЙСТВ МОДИФИЦИРОВАННЫХ ФЕНОЛФОРМАЛЬДЕГИДНЫХ ОЛИГОМЕРОВ. *Universum: технические науки*, (6-3 (87)), 65-69.
2. Xurmatov, A. M., Turdialievich, B. T., & Abdunazarov, F. (2021, October). Numerical Simulation of Fluid Behavior in Ansys. In " ONLINE-CONFERENCES" PLATFORM (pp. 172-177).

3. Qobuljon, A., Ibrohim, R., & Gayipov, A. (2022). METHOD OF DETERMINATION OF FURFURYL ALCOHOL. *Scientific Impulse*, 1(4), 1774-1778.
4. Zokirov, M. (2023). TUPROQ TURLARI VA TUPROQ HOLATINI YAXSHILASH USULLARI. *Yangi O'zbekiston talabalari axborotnomasi*, 1(1), 5-9.
5. Соддиков, Ф. Б., & Мирзакулов, Х. Ч. (2018). Исследование процесса кальцинации гидрокарбоната натрия, полученного из очищенных растворов сильвинитов Тубегатанского месторождения. *Наука сегодня: факты, тенденции, прогнозы». Россия, г. Вологда*, 27, 28-30.
6. Гайипов, А. Р., Нормурадов, И. У., & Таджиходжаева, У. Б. (2020). ИЗУЧЕНИЕ ВЛИЯНИЕ СОСТАВА ФЕНОЛА СПИРТА НА ПРОЦЕСС ВШИВАНИЕ МОДИФИЦИРОВАННЫХ ФЕНОЛ-ФОРМАЛЬДЕГИННЫХ ОЛИГОМЕРОВ. *Экономика и социум*, (12-1), 457-461.
7. Жураев, М. У., Каримов, А. М., & Ботиров, Э. Х. (2022). Scutellaria adenostegia Briq ўсимлиги таркибидаги апигенин (5, 7, 4'тригидроксифлавоноид) ни ажратиш олиш ва таҳлил қилиш. *Ta'lim fidoyilari*, 22(7), 178-179.
8. Rakhmonov, D., Jo'rayev, M., & Zolkirov, M. (2022). PAHTA SANOATI CHANGLARINING KIMYOVIY TARKIBINI TADQIQ ETISH. *Zamonaviy dunyoda innovatsion tadqiqotlar: Nazariya va amaliyot*, 1(28), 412-415.
9. G'oyipov, A. (2022). Termoplastik poliefirlar ishrirokida modifikatsiyalashning afzalliklari. *Eurasian Journal of Academic Research*, 2(7), 191-197.
10. Rakhmonov, D., & Gayipov, A. (2022). STUDY OF COMPOSITION AND CRITICAL PARAMETERS OF DUST FROM LOCAL COTTON INDUSTRY. *International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology*, 2(9), 77-81.
11. Tohirov, M., Sobirova, S., & Shermatov, A. (2022). SIMOBNI ANIQLASHNING SPEKTROFOTOMETRIK USULI. *Zamonaviy dunyoda innovatsion tadqiqotlar: Nazariya va amaliyot*, 1(28), 235-239.
12. Ғойипов, А., Абдухакимов, Т., & Рахмонов, Д. (2022). ЭРИТМА КОНЦЕНТРАЦИЯСИНИ ҲИСОБЛАШНИНГ ОПТИМАЛ УСУЛЛАРИ. *Zamonaviy dunyoda innovatsion tadqiqotlar: Nazariya va amaliyot*, 1(28), 416-420.
13. Mukhammadjon, J., Dilshod, R., & Botirov, E. (2022). ESSENTIAL OIL COMPOSITION OF TWO SPECIES OF SCUTELLARIA AERIAL PARTS FROM UZBEKISTAN AND THEIR ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITIES. *BEST SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH-2023*, 1(1), 208-215.

14. Дадамирзаев, М. Х. (2018). Микробиологические и физико-химические показатели полуфабрикатов овощных соусов. *Universum: технические науки*, (9 (54)), 24-26.
15. Абдуназаров, Ф. А. (2022). Химический анализ состава местного нефтяного кокса и перспективы применения в сфере производства на основе полученных результатов.
16. Jo'rayev, M. (2022). KO'KAMARON O'SIMLIGINING KODENSIRLANGAN FENOLLI BIRIKMALARI. *Zamonaviy dunyoda innovatsion tadqiqotlar: Nazariya va amaliyot*, 1(23), 114-116.
17. Соддилов, Ф. Б., & Мирзакулов, Х. Ч. (2018). Исследование влияния степени аммонизации на изменение химического состава твердой фазы из насыщенных растворов сильвинитов Тюбегатанского месторождения. *Наука сегодня: факты, тенденции, прогнозы*. Россия, г. Вологда, 27, 30-32.
18. Рахимов, У. Ю., Атаханов, Ш. Н., Атамирзаева, С. Т., Хожиев, Р. М., & Дадамирзаев, М. Х. (2014). Использование порошка-полуфабриката, полученного из вторичного сырья соковых производств, в приготовлении мучных национальных изделий Узбекистана. *Молодой ученый*, (6), 226-229.
19. Абдуназаров, Ф. А. (2022). ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЕ ЭЛЕМЕНТНОГО СОСТАВА НЕФТЯНОГО КОКСА МЕТОДОМ АТОМНО-ЭМИССИОННОЙ СПЕКТРОСКОПИИ С ИНДУКТИВНО-СВЯЗАННОЙ ПЛАЗМОЙ PERKIN ELMER AVIO 200. *Universum: химия и биология*, (11-2 (101)), 37-43.
20. Raхmonov, D., & Zokirov, M. (2023). POLISTIROL ASOSIDAGI BETON KOMPOZITSIYALARINI SUV SHIMUVCHANLIK XOSSALARINI O'RGANISH. *Zamonaviy dunyoda innovatsion tadqiqotlar: Nazariya va amaliyot*, 2(1), 21-24.
21. Жалолдинов, А. Б., Соддилов, Ф. Б., Мамаджанов, З. Н., & Турсунов, Л. А. (2021). Исследование распределения химического состава и кальциевого модуля мытого обожженного фосфоритового концентрата Центрального Кызылкума по фракциям. *Universum: технические науки*, (8-2 (89)), 33-36.
22. Абдурахмонов, Э. Б., & Абдуназаров, Ф. А. (2022). ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ ПОЛУЧЕНИЯ ПОРОШКООБРАЗНЫХ МАТЕРИАЛОВ ИЗ ОТРАБОТАННЫХ НЕФТЕПРОДУКТОВ И ГРАНИТНЫХ ИЗДЕЛИЙ В СТРОИТЕЛЬНОЙ ОТРАСЛИ. *Universum: технические науки*, (3-4 (96)), 59-67.
23. Toshboeva, S., Boqirova, F., & Dadamirzayev, M. (2022). Recipe and technology of high viscosity broth for the preparation of semi-finished paste sauces. *Science and innovation*, 1(A7), 305-308.

24. Zokirov, M., Abdug'aniyev, A., & Yusupova, M. (2022). KIMYOVIY ANALIZ USULLARI ASOSIDA O'SIMLIKDAGI FLAVONOIDLARNI ANIQLASH. Zamonaviy dunyoda innovatsion tadqiqotlar: Nazariya va amaliyot, 1(28), 172-175.
25. Doniyor o'g'li, R. D., & Toxirjon o'g, A. T. A. (2023). DEVELOPING THE ABILITY OF STUDENTS IN TEACHING INORGANIC CHEMISTRY LESSONS. BEST SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH-2023, 2(1), 217-225.
26. Zokirov, M., & Gayipov, A. (2023). METHODS OF PREVENTION OF YOUTH INTERNET DEPENDENCE. BEST SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH-2023, 2(1), 83-92.
27. Ergashev, S., G'oyipov, A., & Alimuxamedov, M. (2022). Kompozitsion fenol-formaldegid oligomerlarining tarkibini nefelometrik usulda o'rganish. Science and innovation, 1(A5), 424-430.
28. Azizbek, G., & Muzaffar, D. (2022). Production of polyester based on adipic acid and determination of optimal component ratio of components. Universum: технические науки, (7-4 (100)), 43-46.
29. Шамшидинов, И. Т., Нажмиддинов, Р. Ю., Мамуров, Б. А., & Рустамов, И. Т. (2022). МАРКАЗИЙ ҚИЗИЛҚУМ ФОСФОРИТЛАРИДАН ФОСФОРЛИ ОДДИЙ ЎҒИТЛАР ОЛИШДА СУВ ТОЗАЛАШ ИНШООТИ КАРБОНАТЛИ ЧИҚИНДИСИДАН ФОЙДАЛАНИШ. Research Focus, 1(1), 126-132.
30. Usmonova, Z., Boyturaev, S., Soadatov, A., G'oyipov, A., & Dehkanov, Z. (2018). Processing of calcium nitrate granulated calcium saltpeter. Scientific-technical journal, 1(2), 98-105.
31. Raxmonov, D., & Zokirov, M. (2023). POLISTIROL ASOSIDAGI BETON KOMPOZITSIYALARINI SUV SHIMUVCHANLIK XOSSALARINI O'RGANISH. Zamonaviy dunyoda innovatsion tadqiqotlar: Nazariya va amaliyot, 2(1), 21-24.
32. Зокиров, М. (2022). ЁШЛАРНИНГ ИЗЛАНИШЛАРИНИ ҚЎЛЛАБ ҚУВВАТЛАШ ИЛМИЙ ПЛАТФОРМАСИНИ ТАШКИЛ ЭТИШНИНГ ДОЛЗАРБЛИГИ. Zamonaviy dunyoda innovatsion tadqiqotlar: Nazariya va amaliyot, 1(28), 107-110.
33. Raxmonov, D., Jo'rayev, M., & Zolkirov, M. (2022). ПАХТА СANOАТИ CHANGLARINING KIMYOVIY TARKIBINI TADQIQ ETISH. Zamonaviy dunyoda innovatsion tadqiqotlar: Nazariya va amaliyot, 1(28), 412-415.

